

BuildingControls (708984)

D2.1 Report on the building fleet development process

Commercial Building Prototype Models and Simulations

In this report, modeling and simulation of energy consumptions of five commercial buildings in 3A climate zone are presented. Design Builder software is used for the prediction of energy consumption of each building and understand thermal behaviors of buildings. Design Builder is a simulation program which works with Energy Plus, and it provides a range of environmental performance data such as outside temperature, energy consumption, comfort condition, heating & cooling temperature and HVAC component size. In this project, Design Builder is used to extract some simulation results to form dynamic model of these commercial buildings. Standalone retail, strip mall, warehouse, medium office and large office prototypes are evaluated via Design Builder respectively. Their layouts are shown in Fig 1, 14, 27, 40, 53 below. Almost all possible sources of energy in buildings are considered in the modeling and simulation. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) data are utilized while modeling our buildings [1]. Overall heat coefficient (U , W/m^2K) values of windows, roof and walls are taken from National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and ASHRAE [2], [3]. Building specifications of all buildings is shown in Table 1, 2, 3, 4, below. The operation of Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning system (HVAC), lighting energy consumption and plug and process consumption of the whole buildings have been studied. The criteria which affect thermal comfort of the occupants and energy performance of building have been determined. Fuel consumption and comfort temperatures values are shown in Fig.2-65 as monthly, daily and sub hourly for each building. February and July are chosen as reference months because they represents the coldest and the hottest months of the year respectively. Also the date of February, 23 and July, 17 have determined as coldest and hottest day. Internal gains value are gathered for these day as sub hourly. In the light of these data finally, building annual utility performance of each building have been determined as shown in Table 6. Some of the terms in the graph are explained below.

Air Temperature is calculated average temperature of the air in zone.

Radiant Temperature is the temperature of an imaginary uniform black box that results in the same radiation heat loss to the occupant as the current room.

Operative Temperature is the mean of air temperature and radiant temperature.

Zone Sensible Heating is heating effect of the HVAC system operation on the zone internal gains.

Zone Sensible Cooling is a term due to penetration of relatively cooler outside air into the space through mechanical ventilation.

General Lighting is an internal gains caused by main lighting equipment in the room.

Occupancy is the heat losses from occupant body.

Solar Gain is short wave radiation from the sun that heats a building, either directly through an opening such as a window, or indirectly through the fabric of the building.

BUILDING – 1: Standalone Retail

a) Building Layout

Figure 1. Standalone retail

b) Building Specifications

Table 1. Building specifications of standalone retail

Characteristic	Description	References
Floor Area,m ²	2298 (length 54.25 m width 42.36 m)	*PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Number of Floor	1	
Aspect Ratio	1.28	
Floor to ceiling height, m	6.1	
Window Dimensions, m	25.035 x 1.5 , 2.9 x 2.5 and 25.035 x 1.5 on the street facing facade)	
Window Locations	Windows only on the south street facing façade	
Building Envelope	Description	
Exterior Walls	Mass Wall: 8 in. Concrete+Wall Insulation+0.5 in. gypsum board	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Roof	Insulation entirely above deck	*NREL, Technical Report, February,2011
Mass Wall U-Values, W/m ² ·K	0.857	
Roof U values , W/m ² ·K	0.1930	
Window U-factor,W/m ² ·K	3.23	
SHGC (all)	0.25	
Air Leakage Rate , ac/h	0.27	NREL, Technical Report, February,2011
HVAC	Description	
Hvac system type	VRF,Heat Recovery , DOAS , DCV	
Heating Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Heating system seasonal CoP	2.5	
Cooling Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Cooling system seasonal CoP	3	
Thermostat set point, °C	23.9 cooling/21.1 heating	
Thermostat setback, °C	29.4 cooling/15.6 heating	
Supply air temperature, °C	Maximum 40, Minimum 12	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Internal Load	Description	
Lighting Power Density, W/m ²	17.22	
Occupancy rate ,people/m ²	0.1610	

Plug and Process, W/m ²	5.38	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
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*PNNL: Pacific Northwest National Laboratory *NREL: National Renewable Energy Laboratory

c) Annual Energy Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 2. Monthly electricity consumption of retail

Figure 3. Monthly comfort temperatures of retail

d) February-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulation and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 4. Daily electricity consumption of retail for February

Figure 5. Daily comfort temperature of retail for February

e) July-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 6. Daily electricity consumption of retail for July

Figure 7. Daily comfort temperature of retail for July

f) February-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 8. Electricity consumption of retail for February, 23

Figure 9. Comfort temperatures of retail for February, 23

g) February-Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 10. Internal heat gains of retail for February, 23

h) July-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 11. Electricity consumption of retail for July, 17

Figure 12. Comfort temperatures of retail for July, 17

i) July-Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 13. Internal heat gains of retail for July, 17

BUILDING – 2: Strip Mall

a) Building Layout

Figure 14. Strip mall

b) Building Specifications

Table 2. Building Specifications of Strip mall

Characteristic	Description	References
Floor Area,m ²	2083 (length 91.4 m width 22.8 m)	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Number of Floor	1	
Aspect Ratio	4	
Floor to ceiling height, m	5.18	
Window Dimensions, m	24 windows, 2.13 x 1.5 each and 12 doors, 1.8 x 2.13 each, on the street facing façade with south)	
Window Locations	Windows only on the south street facing façade	
Building Envelope	Description	
Exterior Walls	Steel-framed Wall: 1 in. Stucco + 0.625 in. gypsum board + wall insulation + 0.625 in. gypsum board	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Roof	Insulation entirely above deck	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Mass Wall U-Values, W/m ² ·K	0.704	
Roof U values , W/m ² ·K	0.1930	
Window U-factor, W/m ² ·K	3.23	
SHGC (all)	0.25	
Air Leakage Rate , ac/h	0.5	
HVAC	Description	
Hvac system type	VRF,Heat Recovery , DOAS , DCV	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Heating Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Heating system seasonal CoP	2.5	
Cooling Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Cooling system seasonal CoP	3	
Thermostat set point, °C	24 cooling/21 heating	
Thermostat setback, °C	30 cooling/15.6 heating	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Supply air temperature, °C	Maximum 40, Minimum 12	
Internal Load	Description	
Lighting Power Density, W/m ²	17	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Occupancy rate ,people/m ²	0.086	
Plug and Process, W/m ²	4.31	

c) Annual Energy Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 15. Monthly electricity consumption of strip mall

Figure 16. Monthly comfort temperatures of strip mall

d) February-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 17. Daily electricity consumption of strip mall for February

Figure 18. Daily Comfort temperatures of strip mall for February

e) July-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 20. Daily comfort temperatures of strip mall for July

f) February-Subhourly Energy Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 21. Electricity consumption of strip mall for February, 23

Figure 22. Comfort temperatures of strip mall of February, 23

g) February-Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 23. Internal heat gains of strip mall for February, 23

h) July-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 24. Electricity consumption of strip mall for July, 17

Figure 25. Comfort temperature of strip mall for July, 17

i) July- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 26. Internal heat gains of strip mall for July, 17

BUILDING – 3: Warehouse

a) Building Layout

Figure 27. Warehouse

b) Building Specifications

Table 3. Building Specifications of Warehouse

Characteristic	Description	References
Floor Area,m ²	4572(length 100 m width 45.72 m)	NREL, Technical Report, February,2011
Number of Floor	1	
Aspect Ratio	2.2	
Floor to ceiling height, m	8.53	
Window Dimensions, m	4.91 x 2.61 , on the west facing facade)	
Window Locations	Windows only on the west street facing façade	
Building Envelope	Description	
Exterior Walls	Metal Building Wall Metal Surface + Wall Insulation + Gypsum Board	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Roof	Metal Building Wall	
Mass Wall U-Values, W/m ² ·K	0.857	
Roof U values , W/m ² ·K	0.1930	

Window U-factor, W/m ² ·K	3.23	NREL, Technical Report, February, 2011
SHGC (all)	0.25	
Air Leakage Rate , ac/h	0.19	
HVAC	Description	
Hvac system type	VRF, Heat Recovery , DOAS , DCV	
Heating Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Heating system seasonal CoP	2.5	
Cooling Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Cooling system seasonal CoP	3	
Thermostat set point, °C	24 cooling/21 heating	NREL, Technical Report, February, 2011
Thermostat setback, °C	30 cooling/15.5 heating	
Supply air temperature, °C	Maximum 43.33, Minimum 12	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Internal Load	Description	
Lighting Power Density, W/m ²	8.6	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Occupancy rate ,people/m ²	0.001	
Plug and Process, W/m ²	2.05	

c) Annual Energy Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 28. Monthly electricity consumption of warehouse

Figure 29. Monthly comfort temperatures of warehouse

d) February-Daily Energy Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 30. Daily electricity consumption of warehouse for February

Figure 31. Daily comfort temperatures of warehouse for February

e) July-Daily Energy Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 32. Daily electricity consumption of warehouse for July

Figure 33. Daily comfort temperatures of warehouse for July

f) February-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 34. Electricity consumption of warehouse for February,23

g) February- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

h) July- Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 37. Electricity consumption of warehouse for July, 17

Figure 38. Comfort temperatures of warehouse for July, 17

i) July- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 39. Internal heat gains of warehouse for July, 17

BUILDING – 4: Medium Office

a) Building Layout

Figure 40. Medium Office

b) Building Specifications

Table 4. Building specifications of medium office

Characteristic	Description	References
Floor Area,m ²	4979.6(length 49.92 m width 33.28 m)	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Number of Floor	3	
Aspect Ratio	1.5	
Floor to ceiling height, m	2.74	
Window Dimensions, m	49.92 x 1.3 fon the long side of facade 33.28 x 1.3 on the short side of the façade	
Window Locations	Evenly distributed along four façades	
Building Envelope	Description	
Exterior Walls	Steel-Frame Walls (2X4 16IN OC) 0.4 in. Stucco+5/8 in. gypsum board + wall Insulation+5/8 in.	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Roof	Insulation entirely above deck	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Mass Wall U-Values, W/m ² ·K	0.704	
Roof U values , W/m ² ·K	0.1930	
Window U-factor,W/m ² ·K	3.23	
SHGC (all)	0.25	
Air Leakage Rate , ac/h	0.5	
HVAC	Description	
Hvac system type	VRF,Heat Recovery , DOAS , DCV	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Heating Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Heating system seasonal CoP	2.5	
Cooling Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Cooling system seasonal CoP	3	
Thermostat set point, °C	24 cooling/21 heating	
Thermostat setback, °C	30 cooling/15.5 heating	NREL,Technical Report, February,2011
Supply air temperature, °C	Maximum 43.33, Minimum 12	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Internal Load	Description	
Lighting Power Densitiy, W/m ²	10.76	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Occupancy rate ,people/m ²	0.05	
Plug and Process, W/m ²	8.07	

c) Annual Energy Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 41. Monthly electricity consumption of medium office

Figure 42. Monthly comfort temperature of medium office

d) February-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 43. Daily electricity consumption of medium office for February

Figure 44. Daily comfort temperatures of medium office for February

e) July-Daily Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 45. Daily electricity consumption of medium office for July

Figure 46. Daily comfort temperatures of medium office for July

f) February-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations

Figure 47. Electricity consumption of medium office for February, 23

Figure 48. Comfort temperatures of medium office for February, 23

g) February- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 49. Internal heat gains of medium office for February, 23

h) July- Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 50. Electricity consumption of medium office for July, 17

Figure 51. Comfort temperatures of medium office for July, 17

i) July- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 52. Internal heat gains of medium office for July, 17

Building 5- Large Office

a) Building Layout

Figure 53. Large Office

b) Building Specifications

Table 5. Building specifications of large office

Characteristic	Description	References
Floor Area, m ²	46320 (length 73.15 m width 48.76 m)	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Number of Floor	13	
Aspect Ratio	1.5	
Floor to ceiling height, m	2.74	
Window Dimensions, m	48.18 x 1.4 on the long side of facade 72.56 x 1.4 on the short side of the façade	
Window Locations	Evenly distributed along four façades	
Building Envelope	Description	
Exterior Walls	Mass (pre-cast concrete panel): 8 in. heavy-weight concrete + wall insulation + 0.5 in. gypsum board	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Roof	Insulation entirely above deck	

Mass Wall U-Values, W/m ² ·K	0.857	NREL, Technical Report, February, 2011
Roof U values, W/m ² ·K	0.1930	
Window U-factor, W/m ² ·K	3.23	
SHGC (all)	0.25	
Air Leakage Rate, ac/h	0.3	
HVAC	Description	
Hvac system type	VRF, Heat Recovery, DOAS, DCV	
Heating Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Heating system seasonal CoP	2.5	
Cooling Fuel	Electricity from grid	
Cooling system seasonal CoP	3	
Thermostat set point, °C	24 cooling/21,1 heating	NREL, Technical Report, February, 2011
Thermostat setback, °C	26,7 cooling/15.6 heating	
Supply air temperature, °C	Maximum 43.33, Minimum 12	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Internal Load	Description	
Lighting Power Density, W/m ²	10.76	PNNL, updated on Friday, August 14, 2015
Occupancy rate, people/m ²	0.05	
Plug and Process, W/m ²	10.76	

c) Annual Energy Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 54. Monthly electricity consumption of large office

Figure 55. Monthly comfort temperatures of large office

d) February-Daily Energy Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 56. Daily electricity consumption of large office for February

Figure 57. Daily comfort temperatures of large office for February

e) July-Daily Energy Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 58. Daily electricity consumption of large office for July

Figure 59. Daily comfort temperatures of large office for July

f) February-Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 60. Electricity consumption of large office for February,23

Figure 61. Comfort temperatures of large office for February,23

g) February- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 62. Internal heat gains of large office for February,23

h) July- Subhourly Fuel Consumption Simulations and Comfort Temperatures

Figure 63. Electricity consumption of large office for July, 17

Figure 64. Comfort temperatures of large office for July, 17

i) July- Subhourly Internal Gain Simulations

Figure 65. Internal heat gains of large office for July, 17

Summary

Table 6. Annual building utility performance comparison

	Annual Building Utility Performance		
	Reference Building	Our Building	Error
Strip Mall	607.20 (MJ/m ²)	634.59 (MJ/m ²)	5%
Warehouse	175.86 (MJ/m ²)	183.54 (MJ/m ²)	4%
Standalone Retail	510.99 (MJ/m ²)	526.34 (MJ/m ²)	3%
Medium Office	391.32 (MJ/m ²)	417.18 (MJ/m ²)	7%
Large Office	805.80 (MJ/ m ²)	757.84 (MJ/m ²)	3%

Comparison between Pacific Northwest National Laboratory and our model building annual utility performance are shown in the table above. In building simulation, infiltration rate for each building is picked up as a tuning parameter due to its variation continuously with changing environmental and building operating conditions. Also, HVAC systems are not evaluated component based.

System ID Modeling of Building Fleet

In this part, building thermal model is presented to describe thermal response of a building by using thermal resistance, R and thermal capacitance, C parameters. The idea of thermal resistance and thermal capacitance is similar to resistance and capacitance in electrical circuit area. In other words, heat flow and pressure in thermal aspect is equivalent of current and voltage in electrical area. Several types building models are available in building control area. In this paper, we based on single zone building thermal model without considering neighborhood relationship.

$$C_1^j \dot{T}_1^j = \dot{m}^j C_p^j (T_{sa}^j - T_1^j) + \frac{T_2^j - T_1^j}{R_1^j} + \frac{T_{oa} - T_1^j}{R_{oa}^j} + P_d^j \quad (1)$$

$$C_2^j \dot{T}_2^j = \frac{T_1^j - T_2^j}{R_1^j} \quad (2)$$

where, T_1^j and T_2^j zone air and wall temperatures, C_1^j and C_2^j thermal capacitance, \dot{m}^j supply air mass flow rate and C_p^j specific heat, T_{sa}^j supply air temperature, R_1^j thermal resistance between zone air and wall, P_d^j the total internal disturbance heat gain (lighting, occupancy, solar gains, etc.), and T_{oa} the outside air temperature. P_d^j , C_p^j , T_{sa}^j , T_{oa} values are extracted from Design Builder simulation software. Prediction of C_1^j , C_2^j , R_1^j , R_{oa}^j is conducted via System Identification Grey Box Model. Design Builder software is an adequate simulation tool for obtaining internal gain and building modeling. This software gives us an idea of thermal behavior of building but it is not suitable for controlling a building. Thus, a linear state-space model was created by using Equation 1 and 2 to form model predictive control algorithm.

$$T_{k+1} = AT_k + B_u u_k + B_d d_k \quad (3)$$

$$y_k = CT_k \quad (4)$$

Where T_k is state (including temperature of zones), u_k is thermal input of each zone, d_k is disturbance vector containing solar gain, occupancy, outside temperature etc. System Identification is an approach for building mathematical models of dynamic systems utilizing results of the system's input and output. We use system identification grey box model. Grey box model is used when the physic of dynamic system is clear or the system is expressed as an

ordinary differential equation with unknown parameters just like our state – space representation. Unknown parameters are estimated with grey box model in MATLAB. In our system, known parameters are results extracted from Design Builder software and unknown parameters are thermal resistances and thermal capacitances. The lumped parameters R and C are dependent on the building zone physics (construction material, window-to-wall ratio, equipment type, orientation, etc.) and calculation of their exact values are difficult stuff. Thus, we determine to identify the values of R and C using data collected from the buildings. To achieve this, we solve an unconstrained multivariable nonlinear optimization problem such that the error between the measured zone air temperature and its estimated value from the model is minimized. For this purpose, we formulate the following optimization problem:

$$\min_{P = \{R, C\}} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^{n_z} (T_1^{j,m} - T_1^{j,e}(P, U)) \quad (5)$$

Subject to Eqs. (1) and (2),

where P denotes the unknown parameter vector, k time step, N number of samples, n_z number of thermal zones, $T_1^{j,m}$ measured zone air temperature and $T_1^{j,e}(P, U)$ estimated zone air temperature from model, and U the heating/cooling input vector (due to supply air, ambient temperature and internal gains). These unknown values are found by using system identification grey box model in MATLAB for our five commercial buildings. We have extracted required data such as zone air, wall, supply air temperature and disturbance values to determine lumped parameter, thermal resistance (R) and thermal capacitance (C) of each building modeled via Design Builder simulation program. We have recorded the data through Design Builder with 1-minute interval during 5 days. As seen in Fig 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 our identified model, predicts the zone temperatures of our five buildings. Our system ID results form the basis of load distribution algorithm. For the accuracy of optimum load drop value obtained load distribution algorithm, linear model estimation rate should be high as much as possible. Thermal resistance (R) and thermal capacitance (C) is presented for five commercial buildings in Table 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 below.

System ID Test Result for Warehouse

Figure 1. Comparison between System ID and Design Builder for warehouse

Table 1. Lumped parameter values for warehouse

Parameter	Value
C11	326708.511339490
C21	2255842.87533067
R11	0.0787951973844594
Roa1	0.144216412856758

System ID Test Results of Strip mall

Figure 2. Comparison between System ID and Design Builder for strip mall

Table 2. Lumped parameter values for strip mall

Parameter	Value
C11	46604.0377622158
C21	250224.29733291
R11	0.0287317564934446
Roa1	0.254795112752562

System ID Test Results of Retail

Figure 3. Comparison between System ID and Design Builder for retail

Table 3. Lumped parameter values for retail

Parameter	Value
C11	74541.2680588502
C21	1578523.49827441
R11	0.0594939094557657
Roa1	0.525087209480498

System ID Test Results of Medium Office

Figure 4. Comparison between System ID and Design Builder for Medium Office

Table 4. Lumped parameter values for Medium Office

Parameter	Value
C11	112652.807627645
C21	1069240.13537897
R11	0.0130285343653959
Roa1	0.180842857798959

System ID Test Results of Large Office

Figure 5. Comparison between System ID and Design Builder for Large Office

Table 5. Lumped parameter values for Large Office

Parameter	Value
C11	1742006.37531992
C21	9999803.50361094
R11	0.00218331467177977
Roa1	0.0218339436651992

References

- [1] B. Liu, M. Halverson, D. Winiarski ve M. Rosenberg, «U.S. Department of Energy Commercial Reference Building Models of the National Building Stock,» 2011.
- [2] M. Deru, K. Field, D. Studer, K. Benne, B. Griffith ve P. Torcellini, «U.S. Department of Energy Commercial Reference Building Models of the National Building Stock,» 2011.
- [3] ASHRAE, Handbook of Fundamentals, American Society of Heating Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineering, 2011.